

Attachment

9.1 Effects of Wavelength Selection - using PCA

Attachment Figure 1.1 | Visualization of Used Wavelengths for the Discrete Random Selection Approach – 2 to 40 wavelengths.

Attachment Figure 1.2 | Visualization of Used Wavelengths for the Discrete Random Selection Approach – 50 to 95 wavelengths.

9.2 Descriptive Visualization of HSI Data for Rat Multiccondition (Datasets II, III & IV)

Attachment Figure 2.1 | Comparative Visualization of Spectral Reflectance of Organs from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multiccondition) for Small Bowel and respective PCAs. **a**, dataset II (rat mr). **b**, dataset III (rat ms). **c**, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other. PCAs depict the respective condition class clusters and axes are not standardized.

a dataset II: rat multicondition regular
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

b dataset III: rat multicondition subset
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

c dataset IV: rat multicondition plus
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

Attachment Figure 2.2 | Comparative Visualization of Spectral Reflectance of Organs from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Colon and respective PCAs. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other. PCAs depict the respective condition class clusters and axes are not standardized.

a dataset II: rat multicondition regular
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

b dataset III: rat multicondition subset
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

c dataset IV: rat multicondition plus
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

Attachment Figure 2.3 | Comparative Visualization of Spectral Reflectance of Organs from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Liver and respective PCAs. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other. PCAs depict the respective condition class clusters and axes are not standardized.

Attachment Figure 2.4 | Comparative Visualization of Spectral Reflectance of Organs from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Kidney and respective PCAs. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other. PCAs depict the respective condition class clusters and axes are not standardized.

a dataset II: rat multicondition regular
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

b dataset III: rat multicondition subset
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

c dataset IV: rat multicondition plus
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

Attachment Figure 2.5 | Comparative Visualization of Spectral Reflectance of Organs from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Spleen and respective PCAs. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other. PCAs depict the respective condition class clusters and axes are not standardized.

a dataset II: rat multicondition regular
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

b dataset III: rat multicondition subset
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

c dataset IV: rat multicondition plus
L1-normalized reflectance [arbitrary units]

Attachment Figure 2.6 | Comparative Visualization of Spectral Reflectance of Organs from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Bladder and respective PCAs. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other. PCAs depict the respective condition class clusters and axes are not standardized.

Attachment Figure 2.7 | Comparative Visualization of Spectral Reflectance of Organs from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Omentum and respective PCAs. **a**, dataset II (rat mr). **b**, dataset III (rat ms). **c**, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other. PCAs depict the respective condition class clusters and axes are not standardized.

9.3 Effects of Wavelength Selection - using PCA

Attachment Figure 3.1 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Stomach (rat mr sto). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.2 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Stomach (rat mr sto). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.3 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Stomach (rat mr sto). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.4 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Small Bowel (rat mr sb). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.5 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Small Bowel (rat mr sb). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.6 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Small Bowel (rat mr sb). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.7 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Colon (rat mr col). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.8 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Colon (rat mr col). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.9 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Colon (rat mr col). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.10 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Liver (rat mr liv). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.11 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Liver (rat mr liv). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.12 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Liver (rat mr liv). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.13 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Kidney (rat mr kid). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.14 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Kidney (rat mr kid). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.15 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Kidney (rat mr kid). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.16 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Spleen (rat mr spl). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.17 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Spleen (rat mr spl). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.18 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Spleen (rat mr spl). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.19 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Bladder (rat mr blad). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.20 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Bladder (rat mr blad). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.21 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Bladder (rat mr blad). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.22 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Omentum (rat mr omen). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.23 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Omentum (rat mr omen). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.24 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset II for Omentum (rat mr omen). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.25 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset V (rat phys ext). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.27 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset V (rat phys ext). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

Attachment Figure 3.28 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Frontward Selection on PCA for Dataset VI (pig phys). Starting at 500 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next longer wavelength until 995 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.29 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Continuously Backward Selection on PCA for Dataset VI (pig phys). Starting at 995 nm and continuously adding spectral information from the next shorter wavelength until 500 nm.

Attachment Figure 3.30 | Visualization of the Effects of Wavelength Selection for Discrete Random Selection on PCA for Dataset VI (pig phys). Random selection of a predefined number of wavelengths in the range between 500 and 995 nm - representatively for bootstrapping run 1.

9.4 Effects of Data Normalization - using PCA

Attachment Figure 4.1 | Reflectance and PCA from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Small Bowel for L1-Normalized and Original Values. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other.

Attachment Figure 4.2 | Reflectance and PCA from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Colon for L1-Normalized and Original Values. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other.

Attachment Figure 4.3 | Reflectance and PCA from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Liver for L1-Normalized and Original Values. **a**, dataset II (rat mr). **b**, dataset III (rat ms). **c**, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other.

Attachment Figure 4.4 | Reflectance and PCA from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Kidney for L1-Normalized and Original Values. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other.

Attachment Figure 4.5 | Reflectance and PCA from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Spleen for L1-Normalized and Original Values. **a**, dataset II (rat mr). **b**, dataset III (rat ms). **c**, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other.

Attachment Figure 4.6 | Reflectance and PCA from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Bladder for L1-Normalized and Original Values. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other.

Attachment Figure 4.7 | Reflectance and PCA from Datasets II, III & IV (rat multicondition) for Omentum for L1-Normalized and Original Values. a, dataset II (rat mr). b, dataset III (rat ms). c, dataset IV (rat mp). Spectral reflectance graphs are stacked on top of each other.

9.5 Effects of Hyperparameter Tuning - for t-SNE

9.5.1 Perplexity in t-SNE

Attachment Figure 5.1.1 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for stomach (rat mr sto). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.2 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for small bowel (rat mr sb). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.3 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for colon (rat mr col). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.4 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for liver (rat mr liv). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.5 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for kidney (rat mr kid). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.6 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for spleen (rat mr spl). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.7 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for bladder (rat mr blad). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.8 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for omentum (rat mr omen). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.9 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset V (rat phys ext). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.1.10 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Perplexity for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset VI (pig phys). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

9.5.2 Learning Rate in t-SNE

Attachment Figure 5.2.1 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Learning Rate for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for stomach (rat mr sto). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.2.2 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Learning Rate for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for small bowel (rat mr sb). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

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9.5.3 Early Exaggeration in t-SNE

Attachment Figure 5.3.1 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Early Exaggeration for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for stomach (rat mr sto). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.3.2 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Early Exaggeration for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for small bowel (rat mr sb). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.3.3 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Early Exaggeration for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for colon (rat mr col). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

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Attachment Figure 5.3.10 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Early Exaggeration for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset VI (pig phys). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

9.5.4 Number of Iterations in t-SNE

Attachment Figure 5.4.1 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Number of Iterations for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for stomach (rat mr sto). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.4.2 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Number of Iterations for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for small bowel (rat mr sb). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

Attachment Figure 5.4.3 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Number of Iterations for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for colon (rat mr col). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

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9.5.5 Metric in t-SNE

Attachment Figure 5.5.1 | Systematic Investigation of Different Categories of Metric for t-SNE. Visualized for dataset II for stomach (rat mr sto). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

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9.6 UMAP

9.6.1 Number of Neighbors in UMAP

Attachment Figure 6.1.1 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Number of Neighbors for UMAP. Visualized for dataset II for stomach (rat mr sto). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

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9.6.2 Minimum Distance in UMAP

Attachment Figure 6.2.1 | Systematic Investigation of Different Values of Minimum Distance for UMAP. Visualized for dataset II for stomach (rat mr sto). Visualization with the previous standard value is marked with a black box.

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9.6.3 Metric in UMAP

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